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The newest history of Uzbekistan
in the context of the development of historical knowledge

Abstract: In this article, information is presented and opinions are expressed about the latest historical knowledge of Uzbekistan and modernization in the context of their development.

Key words: History, the latest historical development of Uzbekistan, socialization, spirituality, culture and art, methodology, context.

In the history of mankind, the last quarter of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century marked the beginning of a new period of social and political changes, and it was during this period that Uzbekistan gained the independence of the national state. This situation demanded fundamental changes in the science of history, theoretical and methodological renewal, in a word, to be worthy of the influence of independent Uzbekistan. If the development of new approaches and research methods in the analysis of historical processes is the most important issue before the science of history, being a historian has become a difficult and responsible task in the conflict of these two centuries. Independence allowed historians free creativity and thinking. Historians, like other representatives of the field of social knowledge, radically changed the theoretical and methodological direction of their scientific activities.

During the years of independence, the arsenal of history science was updated and changed. The process of deep internal transformation in the science of history was reflected in the theoretical-methodological, conceptual, substantive and structural changes of the science.

The changes taking place in the world and in our country led to an even deeper observation of the past. In the course of these changes, the important coaching role of history and past experience became more evident. The fact that knowledge of history is necessary not only for an impartial assessment of past events, but also for a correct understanding of the present day and the ability to see the future has been confirmed once again.

Under the influence of new social impulses, many topics began to be observed in a new way. Topics that need Haqqani's interpretation and analysis have been the focus of historians' attention, and this process continues until today to arrive at a firm conclusion about some of its conceptual aspects. Subjects that were forbidden to be studied in the Soviet era, and misinterpreted, were re-examined on the basis of scientific objectivity - from the point of view of national independence. The range of historical research has expanded and new scientific directions have emerged.

The most recent history of Uzbekistan has become one of such new scientific directions in the science of history. It was created directly with the establishment of an independent national state, and it is aimed at studying and analyzing the development of modern historical processes, summarizing the historical experience, and thereby understanding the national identity. The newest history of Uzbekistan has not yet acquired an institutional character, that is, it has not been divided into an independent field of science with its own methodology, research work and educational and methodological support. The scope and development of the events that have taken place in the life of our country during the last years puts forward to science and education the issue

of their systematic observation.

It is known that dissertation research is an indicator of the development of scientific knowledge in the organization of the scientific process. Various aspects of the history of the period of independence have been the subjects of doctoral and candidate theses. It should be noted that there are not many researches devoted to the study of the history of the independence period of Uzbekistan in the proportion of doctoral theses defended in the field of history of Uzbekistan in the specified years.

The step-by-step implementation of fundamental reforms in the political, socio-economic and cultural spheres, recognized as the "Uzbek model" in the world, historical processes were studied step by step by historians and became the object of scientific research.

The democratic changes in the life of the society of Uzbekistan, the means of formation of the civil society, the emergence and development of the multi-party system have been studied by historians.

During the years of independence, changes in the socio-economic and cultural spheres were studied on the example of the republic's regions and cities.

In the years of independence, the study of national characteristics and demographic development processes of the population of Uzbekistan became of urgent importance. The impact of historical changes on demographic processes and the analysis of their various aspects was focused on the formation of a strong civil society implemented in the country, increasing the social effectiveness of reforms.

Historians shed light on the economic, agrarian, and cultural reforms and their results by studying the specific features of the development of a certain area, which is the object of research, during the years of independence. Despite the fact that the periodical boundaries and sources of these studies are different, the summation of these studies serves as an important material in forming a comprehensive picture of the economic, social and cultural processes of the country during the years of independence.

In the conditions of independence, where market relations are settled and entrepreneurship development is given great importance, the study of the processes of restoration of the traditional craft industry and its new development on a national basis has become the research object of historians.

There have been studies that studied various aspects of the social processes of the independence period in a certain chronological framework.

The path of independent development of Uzbekistan required the reform of the education system. In this field, Uzbekistan developed its own national strategy and followed a unique path of reforming the education system. As a result of the process of reforms in the education system, the development and implementation of the National Program of Personnel Training, studies were carried out that shed light on the continuity of education, deepening of general and professional education, as well as analyzing the state of science development and development directions in Uzbekistan.

In the conditions of Uzbekistan's independence, researches have been created that shed light on various aspects of the revival and development of national spiritual values and the development of culture.

The research of G. Ganieva has shown that the success of the democratic reforms implemented in the years of independence depended on the activity of women, who made up a

large part of the society.

The importance of youth policy in independent Uzbekistan and their role in the social and political life of the country, the formation of moral values among student youth in the conditions of national independence were studied.

The place of Uzbekistan in the system of international relations was one of the most actively studied problems among the topics of candidate dissertations. To study the formation and development of the diplomatic service in Uzbekistan. Through the comparative analysis of the history of Uzbekistan's foreign relations during the Soviet period and the years of independence, it was possible to identify the factors that played an important role in the development of this field, and to summarize the historical processes and draw scientific conclusions.

Cooperation of Uzbekistan with international organizations and the problem of Uzbekistan's role in ensuring security in the Central Asian region were studied in a number of candidate theses. These studies will help to comprehensively cover and scientifically illuminate the cooperation relations of the young independent republic with the world community and international organizations in ensuring stability in the region in order to create the newest history of Uzbekistan.

The analysis of the dissertation research presented above showed that it would be appropriate to form a systematic approach to the study of the history of Uzbekistan, to determine certain chronological frameworks based on the characteristics of each process in the study of fundamental changes in the political, socio-economic, and cultural spheres. These studies, the critical and analytical study of the source data embodied in them serve to create a comprehensive picture of the history of Uzbekistan.

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